

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR PREPARING FUTURE EDUCATORS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON A GENDER APPROACH

Shokirova Hilola Abduraxmon qizi

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Abstract. Education creates and forms the conditions for continuous personal improvement of the basic competencies of a modern person. In order to increase the effectiveness of teaching, innovative technologies of education and upbringing, new methods within the framework of subject courses are being developed and implemented by students. The gender approach is becoming an urgent task in these technologies. The concept of "gender" can be defined as a person's belonging to the social gender, which determines his behavior based on social stereotypes. Pedagogical science and pedagogical practice are the most important tasks of the path to mastering the concept of gender in gender relations in society

Keywords: Gender approach, educator competence, seminars and trainings, boys and girls, stereotypes, professional activity.

Аннотация. Образование создает и формирует условия для постоянного личностного совершенствования основных компетенций современного человека. В целях повышения эффективности обучения студентами разрабатываются и применяются на практике инновационные технологии образования и обучения, новые методики в рамках естественнонаучных курсов. В этих технологиях гендерный подход становится актуальной задачей. Понятие «гендер» можно определить как социальный пол человека, определяющий его поведение на основе социальных стереотипов. Наука педагогики и педагогической практики – важнейшая задача освоения гендерной концепции гендерных отношений в обществе.

Ключевые слова: Гендерный подход, компетентность педагога, семинары и тренинги, юноши и девушки, стереотипы, профессиональная деятельность.

Annotatsiya. Ta'lim zamonaviy shaxsning asosiy kompetensiyalarini doimiy shaxsiy takomillashtirish uchun sharoit yaratadi va shakllantiradi, O'qitish samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida talabalar tomonidan ta'lim va tarbiyaning innovatsion texnologiyalari, fan kurslari doirasidagi yangi uslublar ishlab chiqilib, amaliyotga joriy etilmoqda. Ushbu texnologiyalarda gender yondashuvi dolzarb vazifa kasb etmoqda. "Gender" tushunchasini insonning ijtimoiy jinsga mansubligi sifatida aniqlash mumkin, bu esa uni ijtimoiy stereotiplarga asoslangan xatti-

harakatlarini belgilaydi. Pedagogika fani va pedagogik amaliyot jamiyatdagi gender munosabatlarining gender tushunchasini o'zlashtirish yo'lining eng muhim vazifasidir

Kalit so'zlar: *Gender yondashuv, tarbiyachi kompetentligi, seminar va treninglar, o'g'il va qiz bolalar, stereotiplar, kasbiy faoliyat.*

Professional training of future educators based on a gender approach includes a complex methodology, including theoretical knowledge, practical training, pedagogical practice, and cooperation with parents. The training of future educators for professional activities based on a gender approach begins, first of all, with introducing educators to gender knowledge. It is necessary to organize special courses for educators on the concept of gender, its role in society and the education system, to study international experience and national models of gender equality. It is necessary to improve their knowledge by organizing and conducting seminars on gender stereotypes and their impact on child education. The use of a gender approach in the school education system is of great importance for the personal and social development of children. Through this approach, equal opportunities are created between boys and girls, education is provided free from gender stereotypes, and conditions are created for the free development of children's interests and abilities.

The main principles of the gender approach include the following.

1. Creating equal opportunities - creating the same conditions for education and upbringing for boys and girls, an equal approach to the development of their abilities and potential

2. Abandoning stereotypes - It is necessary to eliminate misconceptions such as "Boys are interested in mathematics and technology, while girls are inclined to art and care work".

3. Gender neutrality in games and activities - Not separating toys, materials and types of activities by gender, that is, providing and encouraging children according to their interests, will achieve the goal. Equally involving girls and boys in various activities. For example, if girls are recommended only for "care" professions (teacher, nurse) and boys are taught only for "power-intensive" professions (mechanic, engineer), this will contradict gender equality.

4. It is necessary to take into account and inform parents and educators on gender issues. Expand their understanding of gender equality and adapt their pedagogical approaches. Promote equal treatment of children at home.

5. Take into account gender issues in programs and methodologies. Reflect a gender approach in preschool education curricula, textbooks, and present various social roles in educational materials based on gender equality.

The use of a gender approach in preschool education helps to develop children's abilities regardless of sexual differences. This will be an important factor in their feeling free in society, choosing a profession in the future, and forming their own personality.

Preschool education is an important issue in the development of gender identity in children, which leads to the development and socialization of children. Gender education helps to monitor children's prejudices about men and women. Parents and educators need to set an example in teaching children gender roles, minimize gender stereotypes, and communicate openly.

To effectively implement a gender approach in the preschool education system, it is important to increase the gender competence of educators. For this, special training and seminars should be organized and held. In this case, through role-playing games, educators model various gender situations and discuss how to solve the problem. In the discussion, solutions are found by analyzing problems using real-life examples of gender equality. For example, educators divide into groups and study fairy tales based on gender stereotypes and discuss how they can be changed in accordance with the principle of gender equality.

Another practical aspect of our research is the integration of a gender approach into education. The use of special lessons and topics on ensuring gender equality, protecting women's rights, and expanding their opportunities in teaching is beneficial for students. This is especially true if it is carried out in conjunction with lessons aimed at developing critical thinking, so that girls can understand their rights and opportunities.

It is important to prepare educators through training aimed at developing gender equality and critical thinking. Educators can expand the opportunities for children to express their opinions by creating an educational environment free from gender stereotypes and discrimination.

The synthesis and presentation of data based on children's gender differences was carried out in three stages: preparatory, main and final.

1. Tasks performed at the preparatory stage:

- determine the gender composition of the group and individual lateration profiles of children using neuropedagogical diagnostic methods;
- determine the ratio of children in the group according to gender differences;
- prepare (collect) educational and methodological materials to explain each topic in two ways.

2. Tasks performed at the main stage:

- monitor the perception and processing of information and the performance of tasks and assignments from the perspective of children's gender characteristics during the training process;

- assign tasks to children with the same laterality in pairs or small groups;
- refer children to the completed task on the given topic, which is contrary to their gender characteristics, and observe how they perceive the information.

3. The final stage is to enter information on the work performed and the changes that have occurred into children's development maps

In the process of preparing future educators for professional activities based on a gender approach, practical exercises and trainings are of great importance. Such exercises allow educators to analyze gender-related pedagogical situations, develop approaches that are not based on stereotypes, and organize the educational process based on the principles of gender equality.

Role-playing games, debates, and discussions can be organized to strengthen the knowledge of educators about gender.

The easiest way to implement a gender approach is to work in groups (boys and girls) divided by gender. Although it is absolutely impossible to separate the class team for the entire lesson, since one of the main principles (gender interaction) is not implemented. In every lesson, the teacher cannot use a gender approach in teaching, but the teacher must remember the individual perceptions of boys and girls.

Within the framework of this approach, the implementation of didactic tasks can be organized at three educational levels.

Organization of educational activities based on a gender approach:

1) creates favorable conditions for directing the educational process to the personality of the students, increasing cognitive activity and creating valuable and meaningful gender development of their personality, correctly directing their mental and intellectual development, strengthening their mental health and supporting their individuality;

2) while ensuring gender equality in the organization of the educational process and regulating social relations, it has a positive effect on the consistent formation of observation, design, hypothesis, imagination and creativity skills in students. In classes organized based on a gender approach, the main attention should be paid to preparing educational topics in at least two variations, synthesizing and referencing them, and reinforcing them with the help of games.

The purpose of gender-based professional training is not only to ensure that educators gain knowledge about gender equality, but also to prepare them to implement an inclusive approach in their professional activities. This, in turn, helps to teach children equality and eliminate gender stereotypes. By ensuring gender equality, educators develop equality among children, teaching them to accept the values of social roles in society in an inclusive manner.

Gender education is designed not only to help children recognize themselves as a representative of one or another gender. The relevance of gender education is to form a stable understanding of their gender in a child - I am a girl; I am a boy. And it will always be so.

Currently, the relevance of gender education is very high, since the direction of the gender education program also takes into account the fact that modern society is categorically against the idea that men and women have only a number of advantages depending on their gender.

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